

BUILDING POSITIVE SCHOOL CLIMATE AND SCHOOL HEADS MANAGEMENT STRATEGIES IN PROMOTING TEACHING AND LEARNING INTERACTIONS AND PARENTAL INVOLVEMENT

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ABSTRACT

Researches have shown that students learn best when they are in an inviting environment with a strong school climate. Using descriptive correlation research design and survey questionnaire as a data-gathering instrument, the study determined the positive school climate and school heads management strategies, when combined, affect teaching and learning interaction practices in promoting parental involvement. A total of 1,127 respondents were composed of parents, students, and school staff from secondary schools in districts of Candelaria, Division of Quezon. A perceived positive school climate indicates a high-level equipped environment, and management strategies indicate a large extent in developing school climate. Teaching and learning interactions indicate discipline to a moderate extent. As a result, the majority of the students are prepared to learn and with Approaching Proficiency performance. Parent participation is high, and to a large extent, involvement factors and frequencies of involvement decline from elementary to high school. Positive school climate and management strategies are significantly correlated to the teaching and learning interactions. Multiple regression analysis shows a strong influence of the environment with students' performance and engagement directly impacting the discipline. Positive school climate and school heads management strategies show influence in the promotion of parental involvement. Respondents differ in perception of management strategies, teaching and learning interactions, and parental involvement. The study recommended that the school heads' may continuously focus on promoting a healthy, positive school climate that can contribute to creating an effective learning environment.

Keywords: positive school climate, management strategies, parental involvement, teaching and learning interactions